

Figure 1: A section of the Nazca Lines in Peru at the coordinates $14^{\circ}42'09''\text{S}$ $75^{\circ}10'28''\text{W}$

Alignment of the Nazca Lines with Mountain Shadows

Jan Peter Metz

jan.metz.software@gmail.com

June 2, 2024

Abstract

This article presents an observation suggesting a potential correlation between the Nazca Lines in Peru and the shadows cast by nearby mountains. Specifically, it appears that at a fixed time during sunrise, the sun over the mountains causes shadows to align with different lines as the year progresses. This raises the question: were the Nazca Lines intentionally drawn to track these shadows?

Keywords: Nazca Lines; Shadows; Sun;

1 Introduction

The Nazca Lines are a series of large geoglyphs made in the soil of the Nazca Desert in southern Peru. Their purpose has been widely debated, with theories ranging from astronomical alignments [RTP21] to religious significance [Mas+16]. This paper explores a new hypothesis based on shadow alignment.

2 Related Work

Maria Reiche studied the Nazca Lines for more than 40 years. She suggested that the lines were used as a calendar [Spa12] [RTP21]. *“Maria Reiche found numerous lines, surfaces and figures with an orientation towards the Sun, several stars and the Moon.”* [RTP21].

Christine Richter, Bernd Teichert and Karel Pavelka established *“that there are individual straight lines that are aligned with the Sun and the seven randomly selected bright stars. However, the number of hits found does not justify the theory that the Nasca Pampas are an astronomical calendar system.”* [RTP21]

3 Observation

At a fixed time during sunrise (e.g., every day at 6:34 am), shadows from the nearby mountains cast onto the Nazca plains align with straight lines as the year progresses. Notably, when the shadows are longest, they appear to align particularly well with a formation of lines, as shown in Figures 3–11. The lines can be found at the coordinates $14^{\circ}42'09''\text{S } 75^{\circ}10'28''\text{W}$. The appendix contains a second example where the lines are not directly aligned with the sun, but appear to track the shadows.

Figure 2: When the shadows cast by the mountains are at their longest during the year, they align with line A and line B. Line A maintains the longest alignment over time, while line B aligns with the shadow for a shorter duration.

Figure 3: On July 24th at 6:34 AM, the shadows align particularly well with lines A and B. From the series of screenshots, all taken at 6:34 AM, this is the date when the shadows reach their maximum length.

Figure 4: July 29th, 6:34 AM. The shadow remains roughly aligned with line B, while line A continues to be well-aligned with the shadow.

Figure 5: August 1st, 6:34 AM. The shadows are shorter but remain aligned with line A.

Figure 6: August 7th, 6:34 AM. Line A remains aligned with the shadow.

Figure 7: August 10th, 6:34 AM. The shadow remains aligned with line A.

Figure 8: August 12th, 6:34 AM.

Figure 9: August 16th, 6:34 AM.

Figure 10: Looking down line A towards the mountains in Google Earth [Goo24].

Figure 11: The ShadeMap website. The app uses elevation data to calculate the position of shadows. [Pio24]

4 Question

Were the Nazca Lines intentionally drawn to track the shadows cast by the surrounding mountains? Or is the alignment with some of these shadows a result of the lines being aligned with celestial bodies?

5 Hypothesis

The Nazca Lines were deliberately designed to track the shadows cast by the surrounding mountains at specific times of the year. This alignment may have served as a calendar, enabling the ancient Nazca civilization to read the shadows to determine important dates, track seasonal changes, and identify the summer solstice when the days begin to shorten.

6 Discussion

There are several challenges and considerations when exploring the hypothesis that the Nazca Lines align with the shadows cast by nearby mountains and hills:

6.1 Precision of the Shadow Map

The shadows on the map are calculated based on elevation data, but the precision of these displayed shadows is currently unknown to the author. To test the hypothesis with greater accuracy, high-resolution satellite images would be required for a more detailed analysis.

6.2 Time Sensitivity

A small change in time can significantly alter the position of the shadows. Reading the shadows accurately could have been challenging.

6.3 Partial Explanation

The biggest challenge to the hypothesis is that only some lines align with shadows; many lines remain unexplained. Christine Richter et al. quantified that *"... of these 2308 lines, only 569 point in the direction of any sunrise or sunset ..."* [RTP21]. Could more lines be explained by the movement of shadows, rather than direct alignment with the sun? The Appendix contains an example of this.

6.4 Alignment with Mountains

Are the lines aligned with the surrounding mountains and hills? Figure 10 shows such an alignment. In this case, the alignment with some shadows may be coincidental. This hypothesis could be tested by finding other mountain peaks that align with the lines, but not with their shadows. If such alignments are found, it would suggest that the lines are aligned with the mountain peaks rather than the shadows.

6.5 Sunrise vs. Sunset

Can alignments be found with shadows cast during sunset? Using the shadow map, no such alignments have been found.

6.6 Purpose of Alignment

It is unclear whether the alignments served as a calendar using shadows or were intended to track celestial bodies.

7 ShadeMap

ShadeMap was used to display the shadows on different dates. The time of day was fixed, and the dates were shifted using a scroll bar to look for alignments between the lines and shadows, as shown in Figure 11.

"ShadeMap is a global simulation of mountain, building and tree shadows for any date and time." [Pio24]

"Given a location and time of year, it is possible to calculate the sun's position. ShadeMap then traces a path from each pixel on the map towards the sun. If the path intersects another object such as a building, mountain or tree, the pixel where the path originated will be in the shade. If the path does not intersect any objects, the pixel will be in the sun." [Pio24]

8 Conclusion

This paper shares the observation that certain Nazca Lines align with shadows cast by nearby mountains, leading to the hypothesis that the lines were deliberately designed to track shadows, serving as a calendar for the ancient Nazca civilization. As shown in [RTP21], although numerous lines are aligned with celestial bodies, this only explains a fraction of the Nazca Lines. Considering the shadows cast by mountains, more lines could be explained as being intended to track these shadows.

References

- [Spa12] Amelia Carolina Sparavigna. *Maria Reiche's Line to Archaeoastronomy*. 2012. arXiv: 1210.1170 [physics.hist-ph].
- [Mas+16] Nicola Masini et al. "Cahuachi and Pampa de Atarco: Towards Greater Comprehension of Nasca Geoglyphs". In: *The Ancient Nasca World: New Insights from Science and Archaeology*. Ed. by Rosa Lasaponara, Nicola Masini, and Giuseppe Orefici. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2016, pp. 239–278. ISBN: 978-3-319-47052-8. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-47052-8_12. URL: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-47052-8_12.
- [RTP21] Christiane Richter, Bernd Teichert, and Karel Pavelka. "Astronomical Investigation to Verify the Calendar Theory of the Nasca Lines". In: *Applied Sciences* 11.4 (2021). ISSN: 2076-3417. DOI: 10.3390/app11041637. URL: <https://www.mdpi.com/2076-3417/11/4/1637>.
- [Goo24] Google. *Google Earth*. <https://earth.google.com/>. Accessed: 2024-06-01. 2024.
- [Pio24] Ted Piotrowski. *ShadeMap*. <https://shademap.app/>. Accessed: 2024-06-01. 2024.

9 Appendix

9.1 Example 2

Another example of shadows that seemingly align with the lines is shown in the Figures 12–14. The lines intersect in the north and do not point directly at the sun. These lines can be found at the coordinates $14^{\circ}41'29''\text{S}$ $75^{\circ}06'10''\text{W}$.

Figure 12: April 6th, 6:59 AM. The shadows of the mountain peaks roughly align with one of the lines.

Figure 13: May 1st, 6:59 AM. As the year progresses, the peaks align with another line.

Figure 14: May 19th, 6:59 AM. The peaks roughly align with a line again.